

COMMUNICATION GUIDELINES FOR EUROPEAN RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES:

engaging with stakeholders in Latin America

Communication guidelines for European research infrastructures: engaging with stakeholders in Latin America

Authors:

Sabrina Gaber, Communications Officer, EMBRC HQ;
Rita Costa Abecasis, Communications Officer, EMBRC Portugal / CCMAR;
Adelino V. M. Canário, Director, CCMAR;
Andrés López Lara, Head of the Equipment and Infrastructure Department, National Contact Point – Research Infrastructures; National Research and Development Agency, ANID; Ministry of Science, Technology, Innovation and Knowledge Chilean Government

Contributors¹:

Ronaldo Adriano Christofolletti, Juan Alberto Betanco Maradiaga, Alejandro Buschiazzi, Rodrigo Cevallos, Marcel Chow, Lilliam de Jesús Lezama Gaitán, Zeneda del Socorro Quiroz Flores, Samanta María Espinoza Rivera, Henry Luis López García, Amparo María Aráuz Galeano, Leonardo Mendoza Blanco, Marcus Polette, Isolieth Rivas, Claudia Romano, Ernesto Jose Rosales Baldelomar, Iris Saldívar Gómez, Jorge Samayoa, Dalia Argentina Sánchez Merlos, Jorge Toledo, José Ramón Velásquez Hernández, plus six anonymous contributors

Design: **Barbara Pintar**, Communication Designer, Pintar B, d.o.o.

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Contacts: infoccmr@ualg.pt and secretariat@embrc.eu

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1. The contributors are the individuals who filled out the survey and agreed to make their name and responses public. In the event that the person did not tick the consent box to be listed publicly as an author, we indicated the person as 'anonymous contributor' (only concerns one individual).

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Introduction

This document provides **tips and guidelines to help European research infrastructures (RI) better communicate with potential partners and users in Latin America.**

Potential partners and users in Latin America:

- Scientists and their affiliated institutions and networks.
- Relevant government institutions such as ministries of research or science.
- Industry stakeholders.
- Other relevant groups (eg funders).

These tips and guidelines are intended to be applied by European RI communications officers and interested parties who may support regional communications in Latin America, including Access Officers and RI Managers (among others).

Considering that effective communication works two-ways, this document encompasses two complementary approaches:

1) A proactive approach to give tips on what European RIs can do to reach out to potential partners and users in Latin America;

2) A passive approach to ensure that potential partners and users in Latin America successfully reach out to European RIs, by improving the visibility and clarifying the communications of the later.

This document draws on findings from a survey distributed between July and September 2021 to local stakeholders in countries including Brazil, Chile, Guatemala, Nicaragua, and Uruguay.

Using this document

Structured like a roadmap for a communications strategy targeting Latin America stakeholders, this document includes sections on goals, targets, key messages, channels/activities, and evaluation.

Each section is presented as a step and provides both survey findings and tips, this way providing the necessary background information and tools for European RIs to develop their own strategy for the region (or country/ies within the region). As the region is vast, and stakeholder interests will vary considerably, there is no 'one-size-fits-all' solution.

When feasible, the document provides tips on key stakeholders, networks, institutions, and other contacts in Latin America (see Appendix 2). Yet these should only be considered as a basis to build from. We strongly advise that comprehensive research is done when including Latin American stakeholders as potential partners and users of a European RI.

Executive summary

Key survey takeaways

Survey findings are incorporated into the guidelines. A few key findings can be highlighted here. There is an apparent desire to collaborate and partner with EU RIs, primarily to gain access to state-of-the-art equipment and services in Europe, as well as staff exchanges. Funding for this type of 'access' is limited or currently unavailable; as such, collaboration agreements and/or memorandums of understanding (MoUs), which would enable Latin American stakeholders to access EU RI services, were indicated as desirable by many participants. It should not be presumed (by our EU RI peers) that Latin American stakeholders are another potential market for EU RI services, whereby services would be paid for at full market cost. Given funding constraints, as well as legal, political, and potentially linguistic challenges, a more holistic approach to engaging with Latin American stakeholders seems more appropriate.

In some cases, respondents indicated difficulty knowing which RI to get in contact with, who to contact, and how to get in touch (and/or follow up). Potential solutions for enhancing EU RIs' communication in this regard, as well as their visibility (to be more 'findable') are thus also included below.

Guideline structure/overview

The guidelines are structured like a communications strategy, providing steps and tips to develop context-appropriate communications to enhance engagement with Latin American stakeholders. In sum:

Step 1: Do your homework

- Identify and read background materials, identify any existing collaboration with other RI's (and reference this information in your strategy!)

Step 2: Identity your goals

- Know that your goals might not be your targets' goals (ie they might not care about you increasing your international service use by 10%!)
- Make sure that everyone in your RI is on the same page in terms of goals

Step 3: Get to know your targets

- Get in touch with your RI peers to identify potential targets (as they may be the same as those in existing collaborations/projects with other RI's – or not, but your RI peers will likely be able to point you in the right direction)
- Consider all targets (ie primary and secondary targets): while you may want to engage with researchers directly, sometimes it can make more sense to reach them via another target (eg their university network); and there are likely other targets you might not think of, which may be very important in disseminating information and/or enabling collaboration (like funders, governments, etc.)
- Personalise your messages for each target – choose your words/messages appropriately for each. That might mean using less scientific/technical language for policymakers, or using the local language (Spanish/Portuguese) for researchers

Step 4: Develop your key messages

- Keep in mind that people have differing understandings of an RI, so start with a basic definition, supported by examples. And consider if you even need to use the term! It might just lead to greater confusion initially. Ease your audience into the concept if it's novel – and recognise that some stakeholders think they have a local equivalent, some don't (realistically, they don't, as an RI is a European invention, but there may be similar kinds of networks in one or more countries)
- Highlight your RI's specific areas of research in a short (1-2 sentence) summary
- Develop messages to grab stakeholders' attention using phrases, collaboration like 'funding opportunity', 'knowledge-sharing opportunity', collaboration
- Make sure your key messages for international/Latin American targets are included in the relevant website section (see below)

Step 5: Identify relevant activities, tools, channels

- Make it easy to find relevant information for international/Latin American targets on your website, social media, etc. (again, consider language – you may want to translate bits!)
- Use websites/blogs targeting Latin American stakeholders to disseminate information; similarly, identify local newsletters and those for relevant H2020 projects
- Use social media (within reason/capacity) and tag local thought leaders/relevant accounts
- Create a specific mailing list for information relevant to Latin American stakeholders
- Work with local press/media; participate in local events/conferences/webinars

Step 6: Evaluation

- Develop a roadmap to evaluate and fine tune your regional communications strategy

Guidelines

These guidelines can be considered as a roadmap for developing your own communications strategy for Latin America. This strategy may be separate from (or incorporated into) your RI's annual communications strategy – this will depend on your specific situation and desires.

Step 1: Do your homework (prep work)

Communications strategy section: Introduction

A good starting point is to read relevant literature related to RI collaboration with Latin American stakeholders. In particular, the white paper entitled 'Recommendations towards cooperation between Latin American and European research infrastructures' (available for download here: <https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/white-papers>) will ultimately help you to better understand the regional context, and to be aware of existing RI efforts to develop collaboration with Latin American stakeholders.

In addition, we recommend getting in touch with European RI peers, as well as individuals involved in Horizon 2020 projects (if different), to identify individuals who have already developed or are developing collaborations with Latin American stakeholders. These EU stakeholders will likely have information on key contacts, relevant approaches (including relevant targets, messaging, and channels), best practices, lessons learned, and more.

Tip: In your communications strategy, reference any background materials and examples of collaboration (obtained through your 'prep work') in the introduction

Depending on how you develop your strategy (as a separate document, or incorporate it into your RI's main communications strategy), your introduction may contain different elements of information. In regard to Latin America, you can provide information on what your organisation has done there already, what 'prep work' you have done in preparing for the Latin American strategy (eg the pre-reads and background work suggested above), and other factors to consider – such as your RI's current communications resources, strengths/weaknesses, lessons learned or best practices from relevant projects of initiatives, and so on.

Why do you need to write this down?

The purpose of having a written communications strategy is to set the tone and direction so that all communication activities, products, and materials are deployed to achieve the desired organisational goals. With an agreed-upon communication strategy, staff and partners have a map they can refer to through the various development and implementation stages.

What if my RI wants to target other geographic regions, not just Latin America?

You can certainly have a single 'international communications' strategy for different countries/regions. However, keep in mind that your strategy will need to be adapted to each specific context. Within a single geographic region (eg Latin America), you may find that you have to deploy various activities through diverse channels (based on behaviour/preferences in a given country); so expect that your international strategy will not be 'one sizes fits all' or even 'fits most'.²

² Note that there are white papers for Africa and Australia (<https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/white-papers>).

Step 2: Identify your goals

Communications strategy section: Goals

This step involves defining your communications objectives, which need to be in line with your organisational/business objectives. Ask yourself: What do you want to achieve by engaging with Latin American stakeholders? Do you want to actively pursue potential users in Latin America? Or do you want to make your service offer better known so that users/institutions can come to you? Note: you can have more than one goal.

Tip: Know that your goals might not be your targets' goals

Keep in mind that even if your business goal is to increase users by 'tapping into' the Latin American market, this might not be their goal, and if presented as such, it may be off-putting. So part of developing your communications goals will require an understanding of your targets' goals, interests and needs. So, for this section of your strategy, we recommend that you focus on joint goals – keeping in mind what your targets would also like to achieve (eg networking, collaboration, joint activities). However, if you have a specific business goal (eg 10% of service requests among international/Latin American users; 50% increase in international collaboration agreements), you can include this information here. Remember that your communications strategy is not your business strategy, yet the former serves to help achieve the latter.

Tip: Make sure everyone in your RI is on the same page in terms of goals

While it may go without saying, all RI stakeholders involved in your Latin American communications strategy should share a common understanding of your RI's goals in terms of communications for the region. (You may consider presenting the strategy to your team prior to implementation; this would also be a good opportunity to identify roles, responsibilities, and other relevant information.)

Insights from Latin American stakeholders...

Main interests and goals of Latin American partners and users

In the survey, many participants ticked the following options (from a set list) for their main interests and goals:

- Gain access to equipment/services that are otherwise unavailable in their home country
- Organise/participate in knowledge exchange activities
- Attract international funding
- Establish formal collaboration agreements
- Develop joint projects

In addition, respondents indicated elsewhere that they were very interested in staff exchanges, networking, and collaboration to further their knowledge and access to more sophisticated equipment.

‘Despite the fact that there is very modern equipment in the region, the expert professionals and knowledge in the development of these methods is deeper in Europe. The interest in collaborating is mainly to gain knowledge to design and carry out better experiments, beyond the equipment, to get to know people’.
- Jorge Toldeo, scientific director of Red de Equipamiento Científico Avanzado REDECA, Universidad de Chile

Survey answers are indicative of a strong desire for collaborative initiatives, rather than sheer paid use of EU RI services. In fact, survey respondents did list ‘financial constraints in paying for EU RI services’ as a main constraint in engaging with EU RIs.

Step 3: Get to know your targets

Communications strategy section: Targets

Before we dive into this section, note that targets are not necessarily the future potential/current users. The targets are the people or entities (organisations, networks, etc.) who you need to get your information to. There are all kinds of targets, and these can be classified or ranked according to relative importance/hierarchy (ie primary and secondary targets, see below).

Tip: Connect with other RI peers to identify potential targets

You might have already done this during your 'prep work' (Step 1 above)! But the idea here is to connect with RI peers to identify the specific people or groups to target.

- The white paper mentioned in Step 1 is a starting point (as well as any discussions you had with other RIs during your prep work).
- You can also use the RI Slack channel (use this link: <https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/slack> or email any available lists for life-science RI's or environmental RI's (ENVRI Community) to ask specifically about targets.
- If you are aware that an EU RI is already collaborating with your target country/ies, contact the relevant RI stakeholder(s), asking them about their experience, the status of the collaboration, and, based on your needs/goals, who the pertinent targets would be.

When relevant (eg after or while mapping out all potential targets, see below), you can ask your EU RI peer(s) to make an initial introduction to the Latin American target(s) (if prior contact exists). There are two reasons for this: the introduction will likely help you to get your 'foot in the door' more easily, and, because of General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)³ 2016/679, providing personal information including names/email addresses is problematic.⁴

Tip: Know your primary and secondary targets

When developing your communications strategy, it is important to not only know your targets, but to designate primary and secondary targets. Before you initiate collaboration in Latin America, you should identify who you are primarily targeting (note: this may change over time).

Keep in mind, however, that if your primary target is researchers, you may also need to target government entities, as they may play a key role in authorising international collaboration and/or may control funding for certain activities (including the use of EU RI services). As such, they may be your secondary targets. Networks and associations may be a crucial way to get information about opportunities to researchers and, as such, may qualify as primary targets.

3. GDPR is a regulation in EU law on data protection and privacy in the European Union and the European Economic Area.

4. For the purpose of the survey, we asked our respondents to name individuals who may be interested in working with EU RIs – we received many answers, but, for GDPR reasons, we cannot share this information in this document. The takeaway is that there is indeed great interest and many potential individuals/groups who would like to EU RIs.

Insights from Latin American stakeholders...

Who to communicate with in Latin America?

Survey respondents indicated the following targets in Latin America (non-exhaustive list, see Appendix for more details):

- Research centres and institutes, specialised laboratories, research centres within a specific university department
- Universities
- Councils of science
- Individual researchers from universities; doctoral students
- Professionals who work for programmes and projects (which are currently working with, have worked with, or potentially interested in working with EU RIs)
- Training or facility manager(s), and Latin American staff scientist(s)
- Ministries in Latin America (science, research, innovation, etc.)
- Networks

Tip: Identify any local networks and databases

A 'short cut' to finding targets' contact information is not only consulting your RI peers but also identifying local databases or mappings. For example, Alejandro Buschiazzi, Institut Pasteur de Montevideo, principal investigator (PI), Uruguay, noted that the Latin American network Centro de Biología Estructural del Mercosur, [CeBEM](#) is currently collaborating with Instruct ERIC to generate a landscape analysis of available RIs in structural biology and protein science in Latin America, and to map out Latin American researchers' needs. According to Buschiazzi, 'A database is being generated, and we have already pinpointed > 150 scientists (names, affiliations)'. For a list of targets per country, see the Appendix.

Tip: Personify your targets to craft relevant key messages

After you identify your targets, try to characterise them. This exercise will help you to understand the messages to craft for each persona (target group) and the channels to reach them most effectively.

To better understand your targets, you can ask questions like: What are their interests? How do they operate? How old are they? What social media platforms, if any, do they use? Facebook? Twitter? Do they have money for funding research? What do they want? How can European research infrastructures better serve Latin American scientists?

Insights from Latin American stakeholders...

Local stakeholders' views on European RIs

We asked, in the survey, how could European RIs better serve Latin America stakeholders, and the responses were extensive, with key themes/words including 'mutual benefit', solid 'engagement', 'collaboration', 'networks', and opportunities for internships, staff exchanges, training, research, and capacity building.

For example, respondents said that RIs should focus on:

- “Facilitating access to their infrastructures, generating new / more channels for open science. Sharing contacts and knowledge, receiving LAC research(ers) in their infrastructures, etc.’ - Claudia Romano, Uruguayan Agency for International Cooperation
- “Establishing more solid engagements, ones that are built based on mutual interest to address global issues. Avoid what could be called “charity” ... sustainable collaboration should provide benefits to both parties... - Alejandro Buschiazso, Institut Pasteur de Montevideo, Uruguay
- “Developing joint projects with equity in the involvement of researchers and scientific publications’ - Juan Alberto Betanco Maradiaga, UNAN Managua, Nicaragua
- “Supporting capacity building processes, forming collaboration networks’ - Ronaldo Adriano Christofolletti, Federal University of São Paulo (UNIFESP), Brazil

The need for funding and scholarships was also emphasized. For European RI stakeholders, we recommend striving to understand how existing financing programmes work in Latin American countries, and exploring ways to make EU RI services eligible for those national (or regional) funding schemes.

- “The ideal thing in my opinion is that there are funded programmes for exchanges, similar to the Janelia Farm model... They should also be better aligned with local financing programs, since in Chile there are scholarships for postgraduate students, for stays and short courses, but they very rarely consider a facility as an option and in general they look for laboratories willing to collaborate. It would be good to have a clear offer of places and technologies to which you could apply, which should include equipment and advice’. - Jorge Toledo, Red de Equipamiento Científico Avanzado (REDECA), Universidad de Chile

Tip: Always keep local language/identities in mind

It is important that all your communications materials/actions keep local language/identities in mind. This is more than simply translating information into Spanish or Portuguese; it is a reminder that each country, each region has its own cultural 'prism' or lense, and it is important to consider those local perspectives and recognise that the EU RI perspective may differ.

'All your outreach effort should consider language diversity and local identities' (anonymous contributor from Uruguay).

Tip: Identify possible obstacles to communication/collaboration

During your target characterisation exercise, try to understand if your targets perceive or experience eventual obstacles to collaborating and/or communicating with EU RIs. This will help you to devise a communications strategy that overcomes/bypasses those obstacles.

Insights from Latin American stakeholders...

Perceived obstacles to communication / collaboration

Participants indicated various perceived constraints in engaging with EU RIs, including:

- Financial issues (lack of funding, or lack of awareness of funding opportunities for using EU RI services, and/or how existing national funding could be used for this purpose)
- Logistical constraints in accessing EU RI services
- Understanding which are the EU research infrastructures they should contact
- Cultural or language barriers
- Training / capacity building needs
- Understanding which are the EU research infrastructures they should contact

While financial constraints are the main limitation for researchers, understanding which RI to contact (and how) seems to be the biggest problem for government stakeholders and networks. For a complete visual representation of the main interests/goals for each main stakeholder group, as well as the main constraints each group may have in engaging with European RIs, see the Appendix.

To conclude, Latin American users may face financial constraints in using EU RI services, and, as such, they may be more interested in developing collaborative activities whereby they can learn from their European peers (and vice versa). The last point, on difficulty understanding which EU RIs to contact (and who within those RIs to contact) will be addressed in the section 'Making your RI more accessible'.

Step 4: Develop your key messages

Communications strategy section: Key messages

Based on your target analysis, you can now develop your key messages and determine appropriate communications channels and actions (Step 5). Depending on your organisational goals, you can consider what type of approach is most appropriate for your target group(s): passive, whereby you aim to enhance your RI's communication to make it easier for Latin American stakeholders to reach you; or active, whereby you actively target Latin American stakeholders to pursue collaboration.

What are key messages? They are the most important statements that you want to share with your target audiences. They should be tailored specifically to target audiences' interests and motivations, hence the personification exercise proposed above.

Tip: Keep in mind that people have differing understandings of an RI

When developing your key messages, keep in mind that there are differing views of the definition of an RI in Europe (and among EU RI internal stakeholders, even within the same RI!). This divergence can be anticipated among Latin American stakeholders, even within the same country, as illustrated by survey responses.

Insights from Latin American stakeholders...

The RI concept in Latin America

In response to the questions (summarised here): 'Do you have a compatible term for an RI' and 'Are relevant stakeholders aware of the concept of an RI', we can see quite a bit of divergence, with roughly 60% of respondents believing a compatible term exists, and about 50% believing that relevant stakeholders are aware of the RI concept (see Figures below).

1: Number of participants who perceive that there is (yes) or there is not (no) a compatible term for "research infrastructure" in their region (n=26).

A country example: a select number of Nicaraguan respondents said that there is not a compatible term to describe a research infrastructure, while others from the same country referred to 'REDECA' and 'Plataformas UC' (Jorge Toldedo) and 'Centros de Investigacion' (research centres) (Amparo Maria Arauz Galeano).

Or, in Brazil, one anonymous contributor said that the term 'research infrastructure' is indeed known, and that it refers to 'physical or virtual facilities that provide the scientific community with inputs, equipment, and users'. However, another Brazilian stakeholder, Marcus Polette, responded that this is not a compatible term to describe a research infrastructure in the country/region.

Figure 2: Awareness of the RI concept by stakeholders in Latin American countries, as perceived by the survey participants (n=26).

Thirteen of the answers were a simple 'yes', five were a simple 'no', and the remaining eight answers provided minimal detail, eg 'Many are, but also a large fraction are not aware (including amongst researchers as well as policy/decision-makers' (Alejandro Buschiazzo, Uruguay). It is good to keep in mind that while researchers may be the main target, it is important that local/regional policy/decision-makers are also aware of the 'RI concept', as they will likely be involved in funding opportunities for collaboration with European RIs.

Tip: Start with a basic definition, supported by examples

Given that the concept of 'research infrastructure' is not familiar nor consensual worldwide, it is recommended that when engaging with regional stakeholders, you use a common definition. Assume that even if stakeholders think they understand the term 'RI' (and/or that a compatible term exists), explain it in simplistic, understandable terms (see the RI-VIS communications toolkit here: <https://ri-vis.eu/download/?file=RI-VIS+Communication+Toolkit.pdf&do=do> and here: <https://toolkit.ri-vis.eu/home>).

You can use your own RI as an example, or, alternatively, an RI that is perhaps more well-known. Here is an example of a small text explaining what an RI is:

“What are research infrastructures, or RIs? A European concept, they’re essentially organisations which may be located at a single site, or bring together research centres in different countries, to provide services, facilities, or expertise to researchers. One well-known example is [CERN](#) (the European Organization for Nuclear Research), one of the world’s largest and most respected centres for scientific research. CERN provides a unique range of particle accelerator facilities to researchers, to advance the boundaries of human knowledge. Our organisation, [EMBRC](#) (European Marine Biological Resource Centre) (insert your own organisation here) is also an RI, albeit it one with multiple sites, unlike CERN (more than 45 in all!). EMBRC provides access to marine resources, as well as services and facilities that allow researchers, from both academia and industry, to study the ocean and develop innovative solutions to tackle societal issues (adapt your description based on your activity).”

Tip: Hold off referring to ‘research infrastructures’ (if relevant)

Yes, the point is to build collaboration between EU RIs and Latin American RIs. Yet, as the survey to regional stakeholders reveals, there is not necessarily an exact replica in Latin America – there are diverse understandings of what the equivalent would be, and not all stakeholders agree on what one is. That said, you might consider avoiding the term ‘research infrastructure’ in initial communication, at least until you have a chance to clarify what it means in Europe. Focus on what your RI does, and what kind of collaboration you’re looking to develop. Then, as a second step, and as relevant, you can introduce the European RI concept using the tips above and terminology from the RI-VIS communications toolkit.

Tip: Highlight the specific research areas of your RI. Prepare a 1 or 2-sentence, simple phrase presenting what you do, and your research areas

It is recommended that you highlight the specific research areas of your RI, as this may not be obvious to your potential targets. If you focus too much on your identify as an RI, you may overlook communicating about the actual research you’re facilitating. As suggested by one respondent:

‘Provide information about the main focus areas of research’ - Leonardo Mendoza Blanco UNAN-León, Nicaragua

When presenting yourself, focus on key messages about what you do, and what you can offer Latin American researchers. For example:

We are EMBRC (insert your RI name) and we support marine biology and ecology research. Examples include X, Y, Z (list research areas here)’.

So, to summarise: introduce yourself, what you do (using the term ‘research infrastructure’ or not, based on your audience), and then dive into the key messages!

Tip: Craft specific messages or 'catch phrases' to grab stakeholders' attention

Think of this as the initial entry point – how you are going to get into the door (figuratively speaker) and get stakeholders to listen. The key is to incorporate wording based on targets' needs and to anticipate their perceived constraints.

Insights from Latin American stakeholders...

Key messages that will capture the attention of Latin American researchers

The key messages that respondents recommended to capture local scientists' attention and get them interested in EU RIs included:

- Funding opportunities (several respondents)
- Knowledge-sharing opportunities (several respondents)
- 'Short messages using "internationalization", "collaboration" and "use of laboratories, equipment and other opportunities" as to "highlight more than the infrastructure"' (Ronaldo Adiano Christofolletti, Federal University of São Paulo (UNIFESP), Brazil)
- 'Innovation, open science, grants, share, work together' (Claudia Romano, Uruguay)
- 'I believe that figures (photographs, videos, animations) showcasing the actual instrumentation that is being made available, is a really attractive way of explaining their specs and applicability. Again, if access and funding procedures are simple, their upfront explanation will also be a powerful way to capture potential users' attention, as these are often the main fears scientists have, when reaching out for assistance'. (Alejandro Buschiazzi, Uruguay)
- Technological innovation, entrepreneurship, joint projects, capacity building, internships (Amparo Maria Arauz Galeano) Tip: Include phrases/keywords that reflect two-way interaction (collaboration) and the ease of working with your RI

Tip: Include phrases/keywords that reflect two-way interaction (collaboration) and the ease of working with your RI

Based on the findings of the survey, it is recommended to develop messages focusing on the ease of accessing/using research infrastructures (and in particular yours!), and to anticipate any funding requirements or political issues that may deter potential users from reaching out. This means that you would need to do some 'homework' on funding opportunities and present the information in a clear way to the targets. If the targets feel as if they're 'left to their own devices' for funding, this could be a strong deterrent.

Messages should assuage Latin American scientists' (and other targets') possible fears that access and funding procedures will be overly complicated. In addition, the tools/facilities/equipment/services that RIs offer should be presented in a visually appealing, easy-to-understand way. As stated earlier in this document (see introduction), there is seemingly less interest in simply paying for EU RI services, as opposed to engaging in collaboration, be it knowledge-sharing, or joint work.

As such, when reaching out to stakeholders, you could include phrases like:

- 'Opportunity to partner with (insert name here) to take your research to the next level'
- 'Opportunity to engage in knowledge-sharing and staff exchanges with (insert name here)'
- 'We have some great equipment, and don't worry, the application/access procedure isn't that complicated. Worried about funding? Don't be!' (note: this should not imply that access is free-of-charge, but the message should at least relay the idea that funding will not be a huge obstacle).

Tip: include supporting materials/links and make materials easy to find on your website

When communicating these messages, or others, to your targets (via email, social media, or other, see channels section below), make sure to include appropriate links to your website, where this information should be visible and clear.

To improve visibility, you could consider having a **new main tab for 'International users'** or something along those lines. Here you could include information on how international users can pay for EU RI services, and include any information regarding special rates or discounts for specific countries/regions, if applicable.

You could also include **user stories** here, and/or examples of existing international partnerships, MoU's, collaboration agreements, and so on. The messaging of 'We are open for business to international users' will be more poignant, in effect, if you can point to examples of previous collaboration. (Admittedly, this will not be possible until you have had at least one international user experience.)

This strategy is applicable for both 'active' and 'passive approaches' – even when you are not actively reaching out to international stakeholders, you should make it easy for them to find the information they need on your website to consider collaboration.

Step 5: Identify relevant communications activities, tools, and channels

Communications strategy section title: Activities, tools and channels

Once you have identified your targets and relevant messages, you can determine which communications tools, activities, and channels are appropriate to get your messages to your targets. This involves thinking about what information to convey and how (ie via social media, newsletters, websites, media outreach).

This step is two-fold: it includes the proposed communications actions to actively reach out to international targets, as well as the actions to enhance information on the RI's own existing channels (eg website, social media) to make it known that international collaboration is possible and that 'we're open for business'.

WEBSITE

Tip: Make it easy to find relevant information on your website (and node websites) and make yourself findable!

If your future potential Latin American partners can't find you online, or they can, but leave your website scratching their heads in confusion, you have a problem. Here are some ideas for enhancing your website:

- **Dedicated section:**

- › Add a section to explaining how your organisation currently works with international users.
- › Feature user stories once they exist.
- › Make contact information visible.
- › You could add a short explanatory video of how international collaboration with your RI works – what are the advantages, what both parties gain, and how the 'access process' works (from project development, to implementation, and so on).
- › Any information on the cost of services for international users (and potential funding sources per region) is recommended.
- › To ensure that you're easily findable online, you could consider conducting an SEO (search engine optimisation) audit, and improving the quality/quantity of search engine traffic to your website

- **Focus on messages:** Remember to incorporate the messages you developed for your target(s) and highlight the benefits of EU/ Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC) collaboration, as suggested by one survey respondent:

'Show the relevance for the work in partnerships between LAC and EU. Consider the specific capabilities and realities between LAC and EU. It is important that all LAC countries could access European funds' - Claudia Romano, Uruguayan Agency for International Cooperation

- **FAQ page:** Consider having an FAQ on the RI website specifically addressing international collaboration questions and in particular those related to funding
- **Funding/calls:** Again, funding is a primary concern, so make sure that any information related to funding (either provided directly by the RI, or available via funding agencies/bodies in Latin America) is presented clearly. If you (ie the EU RI) has a call, or are publicising a call, make sure that the procedure is clear. This particular recommendation is based on a respondents' feedback:

'Explain the procedure of how to link to the European research infrastructures. In some cases, the launching of the calls is not clear about this procedure' – Dalia Argentina Sánchez Merlos, UNAN Managua, Nicaragua

- **Spanish / Portuguese translation:** To address potential language barriers and reassure Latin American stakeholders, you may consider translating this part of your website into Spanish and/or Portuguese. Again, in the survey we did notice that several respondents responded to the English questions in Spanish; this is likely indicative of a certain comfort level in Spanish (over one's non-native language).
- **Node websites:** If your nodes have their own websites, you could have them add similar information, or simply redirect from their website to the 'main RI website' to find relevant information on opportunities for international/Latin American stakeholders.

Tip: Using other websites/blogs targeting Latin American stakeholders to disseminate information about your EU RI

One respondent (Rodrigo Cevallos, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile) recommended 'Building a common website focused on the potential users'. This would be particularly recommended in the case of a collaboration agreement (with national or regional entities including public and private universities, civil and governmental organisations involved in this process, etc.) (Amparo María Aráuz Galeano, Universidad Católica del Trópico Seco, Nicaragua)

Also, see if your target (in the case of institutions, networks, associations, or any other entity besides an individual) has a website; explore additional websites consulted by your targets. This could include EU project websites with a focus on 'LAC' countries, event websites, or other. One participant (Iris Saldívar Gómez, Universidad Centroamericana, Nicaragua) also suggested disseminating information via the 'culture section' of Embassy websites.

SOCIAL MEDIA

Recommended communications practices on social media include:

- Regularly updating your existing social media channels (Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube, etc.) with information on international collaboration, and specifically on Latin America.
- Encouraging your nodes to ‘engage’ with your social media content on international collaboration to increase reach/impact. Provide additional training to the nodes on how this can be achieved.
- Considering campaigns that support your goals, eg ‘Latin American User of the Month’ (a short video or text/photo highlighting a user’s experience with your RI); or interviews with individuals who participated in knowledge/staff exchanges (including EU RI stakeholders who participated in them – in this way you can show that the benefit is mutual, both sides of the collaboration are benefitting)
- Considering additional accounts that have readership among Latin American stakeholders. For example, one respondent (Iris Saldívar Gómez, Universidad Centroamericana, Nicaragua) suggested disseminating information via the European Union Facebook page.

Insights from Latin American stakeholders...

Social media channels used by Latin American stakeholders

The survey revealed a diversity of social media channels that would be relevant for RIs to reach Latin American users, including, in this order:

Figure 3: Appropriate social media channels for communications in Latin America, as perceived by the survey participants (proportion of responses, n=26).

An interesting takeaway is the prevalence of Facebook, and the relative prevalence of Instagram, a channel on which many EU RIs are not active (or do not have an institutional account).

Tip: Use more than one social media channel, but do not spread yourself too thin!

Rather than creating accounts on all of the channels referenced by Latin American stakeholders (which is hard to do effectively, given typically limited social media/communications resources), you can tailor your approach to your specific targets. By discussing with your RI peers who have experience, or the targets themselves, you can determine where it will be appropriate to include information.

Tip: Identify the local thought leaders, follow relevant accounts

Follow your targets' accounts on social media. Follow their followers (they usually follow back). Ask your targets who are the 'thought leaders' and/or influential scientific personalities on Twitter, LinkedIn, and elsewhere. You can send direct messages to these individuals, if you have not yet been in touch, inform them who you are, and ask them for support in spreading your messages/posts to their followers.

Identify the thought leaders in the Latin American country/ies that you are targeting; tag individuals, networks, universities, or other accounts that have been identified as key targets. See the Appendix for examples from survey respondents.

MULTIMEDIA

Videos: Consider developing a short video: '(your RI's name)-Latin American Collaboration' providing an overview of how international (specifically Latin American) users can collaborate with your RI; this could include different situations, like the development of an MoU (and what that would bring to the country), a collaboration agreement, a joint project, etc. If your RI doesn't have an example yet of this kind of collaboration, you could perhaps focus on RI collaboration in general with Latin American stakeholders, and possibly use their stories as examples (eg Instruct).

Webinars: To attract Latin American users, you could develop a webinar series, targeted as them. Ideally this would be done in collaboration with a local partner, would feature both Latin American and EU RI speakers, and would link to how EU RIs and Latin American stakeholders can work together. A recommended format would be 20 minutes talk, 10 minutes discussion, with talks in English as feasible (to avoid the occasional awkwardness of live translation).

PRINT / ONLINE DOCUMENTS

Brochures: Consider developing a short and long brochure talking about your RI's experience with international users, and any specific experience in Latin America; you could present your goals for the region in terms of joint project development or other, and present the benefits for both parties in engaging in collaboration. Make sure to make it clear why Latin American stakeholders should work with your RI, and why you want to work with them.

Questions to address in brochures (and other promotional materials): What can your RI provide? What is the cost of using the RI? What is the return on investment? What do international users need to apply to use services?

Develop other materials as relevant: if you are going to visit local stakeholders, you can create additional printed materials, you could even translate your RI's slogan into Spanish, and put that on a flyer (or other item like a tote bag – but keep in mind, those cotton bags require a lot of water to make!).

Policy briefing: Consider developing relatively simplistic (minus the jargon!) materials for funders/policymakers communicating the value of working with your RI, and the potential benefits for the country/region in question.

NEWSLETTERS

RI newsletters (and/or joint newsletters): If relevant, you could develop a newsletter focusing specifically on the collaboration between your EU RI and local stakeholders – if an MoU or collaboration agreement has been created with a specific institution, this could be a joint editorial effort, featuring both logos, and you could ask Latin American scientists and EU RI stakeholders (RI director, site service providers, technicians, etc.) to provide editorials, short texts, or interviews. Any scientific articles stemming from collaboration between the RI and the local institution (or 'RI' depending on how they see themselves) could be featured here as well.

Tip: Create a mailing list for your communications materials for Latin America

In addition to asking local Latin American partners to disseminate information, you should also build your own mailing list.

Dissemination via local newsletters and/or those of relevant European (H2020) projects focussing on the region: Consider disseminating information about your EU RI (collaboration opportunities, staff exchanges, services, etc.) via existing newsletters in Latin America.

Tip: Identify local newsletters as well as newsletters for relevant H2020 projects America

Check local stakeholder websites (see section above for tips/URLs for select countries), and see which ones have newsletters. Use the website contact information (or your local focal point) to explore the possibility of including information about your RI in the newsletter. One example is: Nicaraguan Academy of Sciences (E-bulletin: <https://www.interacademies.org/news/e-bulletin>).

PRESS, MEDIA & OUTREACH

Press / media: Draft and disseminate press releases, as relevant; coordinate interviews and press conferences, with both European and Latin American stakeholders. Coordinate with local journalists/communications officers to lead these activities.

As feasible, contact local television networks. One participant suggested, for example, the TV network 'TV Futura' (Marcus Polette, University of Vale do Itajai – UNIVALI, Brazil).

Tip: Identify the communications and/or press departments at target institutions/networks

For example, the Institut Pasteur in Montevideo has a dedicated press office. Contacting the head of this department would be a good starting point to discuss strategy and potential collaboration opportunities for information dissemination/promotion. It will be much easier to tap into local media 'markets' if you have a local contact to assist you with this purpose (they may also recommend local agencies for the purpose of organising press conferences, if they cannot perform this service themselves).

REGIONAL EVENTS

Respondents pointed to university meetings or fairs; webinars; national scientific/technical/technology/educational conferences; and other types of networking or university events as relevant venues to present opportunities to collaborate with European RIs. For a more detailed list of proposed events by country, see the Appendix.

Tip: Participate in local events/conferences/webinars

You can use local events as an opportunity to meet potential users/interested parties, and disseminate information at these events.

Step 6: Evaluation & next steps

(Communications strategy section title: Evaluation)

As for any communications strategy, evaluation is an important step. Anticipate how you will evaluate your regional communications strategy, and when.

Evaluation questions could include the following:

(Note these are relatively generic suggestions, you will need to tailor them to your specific communications objectives/actions, and make them more specific):

- Have we achieved our objectives? If not, what potential factors (internal or external) interfered with the successful achievement of these objectives?
- Did we reach the right audience, and did we use the right tools?
- Were all pre-identified tools used? Or did budgetary or other constraints prohibit the creation of all anticipated tools?
- What worked? What did not, and why? How could we act differently next time?
- Were decisions taken as a result?
- Was the budget respected? Was the proposed budget adequate, or did we under-evaluate the required resources, in an effort to keep the communications budget low?
- Did we achieve our objectives in terms of events?
- How many people signed up for the event?
- How many people ended up attending the event?
- How does the above ratio compare to previous years?
- What was behaviour like on social media leading up to, during, and following the event? How many people visited the event web page? How many people Tweeted about the event? How many new Twitter followers did we get immediately following the event? Was there any press coverage in local/international media?
- Were specific conference objectives reached?
- Did the event lead to any new service requests or new collaboration agreement(s), MoU(s), joint projects, etc.?

Tip: add a timeline to your evaluation

Decide if you will evaluate the success of your regional communications strategy every six months, yearly, or something else.

Appendix

This section contains more detailed information about the respondents (see below) as well as detailed information regarding resources in the region and/or in individual Latin American countries. As we did not have respondents from every single Latin American country, please keep in mind that the resources are just a sample and can give you an idea of the kinds of resources to look for when developing your communications in the region.

Survey

Survey structure

The survey aimed to assess existing level of awareness and understanding of European research infrastructures (RIs). It also sought to identify the main interests and goals, as well as the main constraints in terms of engaging with European RIs for four pre-identified groups:

- Individual scientists
- Research organisations / institutions
- Research networks / associations
- Government entities

Respondents were asked to provide information such as how European RIs can better serve Latin American scientists, what RIs can do to ensure that they are found by researchers and entities from Latin America, what channels are relevant to communicate on, and more. The idea was to gain a global yet detailed look of current perceptions and proposed means to enhance collaboration using tailored, context-appropriate approaches.

Dissemination and respondents

The survey document was distributed to local stakeholders (in countries including Brazil, Chile, Guatemala, Nicaragua, and Uruguay). The survey was in English; respondents replied in either English or Spanish.

Who filled out the survey? The primary 'targets' (or desired respondents) were the individuals who contributed to the RI-VIS white paper 'Recommendations towards cooperation between Latin American and European research infrastructures' (available for download here: <https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/white-papers>), as well as any new individuals recommended by the Organising Committee, and in particular by the local regional stakeholder (Andrés López Lara). EU RI stakeholders including Claudia Alén Amaro and Natalie Haley supported dissemination as well.

In all, 26 individuals responded to the survey, all of whom provided their consent to be authors of these guidelines and to share their findings.

The **country split** for the 26 respondents is as follows: Brazil: 3, Chile: 2, Guatemala: 1, Nicaragua: 17, Uruguay: 3 (see Figure 1).

Indeed, we had a disproportionate number of respondents from Nicaragua. However, the goal here is not to provide a country-by-country analysis of stakeholder perceptions of RIs. Rather the aim is to capture local perceptions regarding RIs to inform context-appropriate communications strategies/techniques. The lead authors/Organising Committee felt as if they could extrapolate the results and make them applicable in general.

Figure 1: Survey respondents by country (n=26).

The majority of respondents were researchers (11) and/or academics (14)*, followed by policymakers / decision-makers (6), RI managers (6), industry (2), and other (2).

Detailed survey respondent list⁵

Name	Affiliation	Position	Country
Claudia Romano	Uruguayan Agency for International Cooperation	Manager	Uruguay
Alejandro Buschiazzo	Institut Pasteur de Montevideo	Principal Investigator	Uruguay
Jorge Toledo	Red de Equipamiento Científico Avanzado REDECA, Universidad de Chile	Director Científico REDECA (REDECA Scientific Director)	Chile
Iris Saldívar Gómez	Universidad Centroamericana	Curator Herbario Nacional	Nicaragua
Leonardo Mendoza Blanco	UNAN-León, Nicaragua	Director of Research	Nicaragua
Juan Alberto Betanco Maradiaga	UNAN-Managua	Coordinador investigación FAREM Estelí (Research coordinator)	Nicaragua
Dalia Argentina Sánchez Merlos	UNAN-Managua	Teacher	Nicaragua
José Ramón Velásquez Hernández	UNAN-Managua	Professor	Nicaragua
Isolieth Rivas	UNAN-Managua	Docente de educación superior (Higher education teacher)	Nicaragua
Marcel Chow	Instituto de Geología y Geofísica - UNAN-Managua	Researcher	Nicaragua

5. Note: this table excludes the six anonymous contributors. Their countries are, however, indicated in the country statistics, as the authors felt as if this information was important and would not jeopardise the contributors' anonymity.

Ernesto Jose Rosales Baldelomar	UNAN	INIES	Nicaragua
Samanta María Espinoza Rivera	UNAN-Managua	Profesora (professor)	Nicaragua
Henry Luis López García	UNAN-Managua	Ejecutivo de Investigación (research executive)	Nicaragua
Lilliam de Jesús Lezama Gaitán	CIES UNAN-Managua	Directora (Director)	Nicaragua
Amparo María Aráuz Galeano	Universidad Católica del Trópico Seco	Dirección de Investigación, Posgrado y Extensión (Research, Postgraduate and Extension Directorate)	Nicaragua
Zeneyda del Socorro Quiroz Flores	POLISAL UNAN-Managua	Coordinadora de Investigación del POLISAL (POLISAL Research Coordinator)	Nicaragua
Rodrigo Cevallos	Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile	Deputy Director for International Research Affairs	Chile
Jorge Samayoa	Universidad Galileo	Director of the Operations Research institute	Guatemala
Marcus Polette	University of Vale do Itajai - UNIVALI	Professor and Researcher	Brazil
Ronaldo Adriano Christofolletti	Federal University of São Paulo (UNIFESP)	Professor	Brazil

Creating the guidelines: approach

Organising Committee

Following a recommendation from the RI-VIS project management team⁶, the task leaders created an Organising Committee, including both EU stakeholders and one regional stakeholder, to oversee the creation of the guideline document. The Organising Committee developed the survey and managed its dissemination and analysis.

This Committee is composed of the following individuals⁷:

- **Adelino V. M. Canário**, Director, Centro de Ciências do Mar (CCMAR)
- **Andrés López Lara**, Head of the Equipment and Infrastructure Department.
National Contact Point – Research Infrastructures; National Research and Development Agency, ANID; Ministry of Science, Technology, Innovation and Knowledge Chilean Government
- **Rita Costa Abecasis**, Communications Officer, European Marine Biological Resource Centre (EMBRC) Portugal / CCMAR
- **Sabrina Gaber**, Communications Officer, EMBRC headquarters

6. Claudia Alén Amaro (Instruct) and Natalie Haley (Instruct) suggested the creation of an Organising Committee; both provided support in disseminating the survey. In addition, Viridiana Beltran Venegas (BBMRI) and Lisa Vincenz-Donnelly (formerly EMPHASIS) also provided support, with Lisa providing a list of initial recommendations for respondents (with input from the white paper author, Meeri Kim).

7. The task leaders are Rita Costa Abecasis and Sabrina Gaber, who are from EMBRC Portugal (CCMAR) and EMBRC headquarters, respectively; Adelino V. M. Canário, director of CCMAR, recommended Andrés López Lara as the regional stakeholder in the Committee.

Targets

Targets per country

Specific examples of potential targets per survey respondent country include:

- **Brazil:**

- › FIOCRUZ, Embrapa, and many others including PNIPe platform

- **Chile:**

- › SEECA, society of specialists in advanced equipment SEECA

- **Nicaragua :**

- › *Consejo Nacional de Universidades, CNU* (National Council of Universities)
- › *Institutions of Higher Education (IES)* attached to the National Council of Universities (CNU)
- › *Ministerio de Salud de Nicaragua* (Ministry of Health)

- › *Consejo Nicaragüense de Ciencia y Tecnología, CONICYT* (Nicaraguan Council of Science and Technology)

- › *Fundación para el Desarrollo Tecnológico Agropecuario y Forestal de Nicaragua – FUNICA* (Foundation for the Agricultural and Forestry Technological Development of Nicaragua)
- › *Instituto Nicaragüense de Tecnología Agropecuari, INTA* (Nicaraguan Institute of Agricultural Technology)
- › *Universidad Nacional Autónoma de Nicaragua, UNAN-Managua* (National Autonomous University of Nicaragua)
 - Suggested contact at UNAN-Managua: *Secretaría General* (General Secretary)
 - Research and Technological Development Unit of *Facultad Regional Multidisciplinaria de Carazo* (UIDT Farem-Carazo, UNAN-Managua)
 - *Instituto de Geología y Geofísica, IGG CIGEO/UNAN-Managua* (Institute of Geology and Geophysics)
- › *Centro para la Investigación en Recursos Acuáticos de Nicaragua, CIRA/UNAN-Managua* (Research Center for Aquatic Resources of Nicaragua)
- *Archaeological Documentation and Research Centre (CADI, Centro Arqueológico de Documentación e Investigación)*
- › *Instituto Interdisciplinario de Ciencias Naturales, Universidad Centroamericana, Academia de Ciencias de Nicaragua*

- **Uruguay:**

'Institut Pasteur Montevideo, beside myself (Alejandro Buschiazzi, principal investigator) and the Executive Director, a key person is ...the head of the Institute's press office'

- **Regional and/or other 'LAC' countries:**

Red motiva (<http://www.redmotiva.com/encuentro-de-investigacion-de-administracion-de-empresas-se-internacionaliza-y-amplia-su-alcance/>)

- › Centor de Biología Estructural del Mercosur (CEBEM) (see below)
- › Tropical Agricultural Research and Higher Education Center (CATIE, Centro Agronómico Tropical de Investigación y Enseñanza) – Costa Rica

- **Entities in Spain/Europe:**

- › Ministry of Universities and Innovation, Spain
- › Nonprofit organisations in Spain promoting Spanish science and technology (which may have an interest in collaborating with Latin America) (eg Fundación Española para la Ciencia y la Tecnología, FECYT)
- › Barcelona Super Computing Center, Almeria Solar Centre (PSA, Plataforma Solar de Almería), a dependency of the Centro de Investigaciones Energéticas, Medioambientales y Tecnológicas (CIEMAT), is the largest concentrating solar technology research, development and test center in Europe

(source: Claudia Romano, Uruguayan Agency for International Cooperation)
earch infrastructures faced by the different target groups, as perceived by the participants.

Target: main interests and goals by stakeholder group

As indicated above, for the purpose of the survey, the Organising Committee identified four stakeholder groups. The figures below illustrate respondents' classification of their goals/interests and constraints for these groups in engaging with EU RIs.

Figure 2. Main interests and goals of the different target groups, as perceived by the participants.

Target: main constraints by stakeholder group

Figure 3. Main constraints in terms of engaging with European research infrastructures faced by the different target groups, as perceived by the participants.

Channels

Relevant websites and online resources (regional and by country)

Survey respondents identified the following as relevant resources :

- ResInfra EU-LAC project website (<https://resinfra-eulac.eu>)
- Red LAC NCP (more info here: <https://www.gub.uy/ministerio-educacion-cultura/politicas-y-gestion/red-lac-ncp>; Twitter account: <https://twitter.com/ncpredlac?lang=en>)
- EU-CELAC Cyted platform (<https://www.eucelac-platform.eu>)
- Bionica.org: Best Practices in Sustainable Agriculture – Biointensive Agroecology (<http://bionica.org>)
- Revista Raices (a Jewish culture magazine published in Spain): <http://www.revista-raices.com/intro/intro.php>
- Nicaragua: FAREM (<https://farem.unan.edu.ni/institucion/>)
- Informative bulletins: Center for Research in Aquatic Resources of Nicaragua; Biotechnology Laboratory, Institute of Geology and Geophysics, <https://www.unan.edu.ni> <https://www.youtube.com/user/UnanManaguaOficial>
- Nicaraguan Academy of Sciences (E-bulletin: <https://www.interacademies.org/news/e-bulletin>)
- Torreón Universitario Magazine
- Revista Universidad y Sociedad (CNU); Boletín Informativo del CNU; <http://www.minsa.gob.ni/index.php/direccion-general-de-vigilancia-de-la-salud-publica/boletin-epidemiologico>; <http://www.marena.gob.ni/>

- › Websites/blogs relevant for disseminating EU RI opportunities, according to survey respondents :

Brazil:

- <https://pnipe.mctic.gov.br/>
- <https://fapesp.br/> As specified by Ronaldo Adriano Christofoletti, Federal University of São Paulo (UNIFESP), Brazil 'Contacting FAPESP would be the best way [to ensure that [an RI] is found by researchers and entities from Latin America looking for collaboration / specific services or a project partner]. FAPESP does agreements with individual institutions of funding bodies'.
- <https://serrapilheira.org/>

Chile:

<https://seecalatam.org/>

Nicaragua:

- › Nicawomantech, Cofidencial.com.ni
- <https://www.csuca.org/>
- <https://www.conicyt.gob.ni/>

- <https://unanleon.edu.ni/>
- <https://www.unan.edu.ni/>; <https://inies.unan.edu.ni/>; <https://igg.unan.edu.ni/>
- <http://www.minsa.gob.ni/>
- <https://www.cnu.edu.ni/>

Uruguay:

- › Institut Pasteur in Montevideo: <http://pasteur.uy/en/home/>

Relevant events

What events did respondents say may be relevant? Note: the information is regrouped by country, yet many of the suggestions (particularly from Nicaraguan respondents) are general and could be applicable for any country in the region.

• Brazil:

- Meetings with the universities in Brazil; webinars

• Chile:

- › SEECA: La Sociedad de Especialistas en Equipamiento Científico Avanzado (<https://seecalatam.org/reuniones-anales-seeca/>)
- National Commission for Scientific and Technological Research CONICYT

• Nicaragua:

- › CNU Higher Education Congress, CSUCA (Central American Higher Education Council) Congress (<https://www.csuca.org>)
- › National education congresses
- › University conference on scientific development
- › Scientific Doctoral Conference
- › University Conference on Scientific Development (JUDC) at UNAN-Managua. Territorial Experiencia developed by the Nicaraguan government in which academics and students of all levels participate.
- › University fairs
- › Webinars with networks
- › Nicaragua Science and Technology Week
 - **Uruguay:**
- › CILAC: Open Forum of Sciences of Latin America and the Caribbean (<http://forcilac.org/en/about-foro-cilac/>)

• Other regions:

- › Cuba Education Congress

Social media

Examples provided by survey respondents include:

- **Chile:** <https://www.facebook.com/seecalatam>
- **Nicaragua:** La Prensa Nicaragua, PEN Centroamerica, Academia de ciencias de Nicaragua, IANAS Latinoamérica <https://www.csuca.org/> <https://www.conicyt.gob.ni/> <https://unanleon.edu.ni/>
- FAREM Esteli (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)
- <https://www.unan.edu.ni>
- <https://www.youtube.com/user/UnanManaguaOficial>
- Revistas: Facebook, Instagram
- AGRIVIRTUAL - CRS (José Ángel Cruz - Jose.Cruz@crs.org); Facebook, Twitter e Instagram; <https://www.facebook.com/consejonacionaldeuniversidades/>
- @mcti, @cnpqofficial, @confapbr, @agenciafaoesp
- Ouvidoria do Mar
- FAPESP

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engaging with stakeholders in Latin America

December, 2021